

Spectrophotometric determination of mercury(II) in environmental (water, soil and biological) samples using 3-methylthiophene-2-carboxaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (3-MTAT)

D. Nagarjuna Reddy and K. Hussain Reddy*

Department of Chemistry, Sri Krishnadevaraya University, Anantapur-515 003, Andhra Pradesh, India

E-mail : khussainreddy@yahoo.co.in

Manuscript received 01 February 2010, revised 10 August 2010, accepted 18 August 2010

Abstract : Analytical applications of 3-methylthiophene-2-carboxaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (3-MTAT) are reported for the first time. The reagent has been synthesized and characterized using IR, NMR and Mass spectral data. 3-MTAT have been used for the spectrophotometric determination of mercury(II). The reagent reacts with mercury(II) in basic medium (pH 8.0, ammonium chloride and ammonium buffer) to form yellow colored 1 : 2 (M : L) complex. The color reaction is instantaneous and absorbance values remain constant for 12 h. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of 3-MTAT method are found to be $1.87 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0107 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ of mercury(II) respectively. The method is successfully applied to a number of water (potable and polluted), biological and soil samples containing mercury(II). The results of the proposed method in the analysis of samples are comparable with those obtained by dithizone method. The method has high accuracy and precision ($s = 0.0042$ for $4 \mu\text{g/ml}$ in 3-MTAT method).

Keywords : Spectrophotometry, mercury determination, environmental, soil, water, biological samples, heterocyclic thiosemicarbazone.

Introduction

Thiosemicarbazones are interesting analytical reagents¹⁻³. Although monothiosemicarbazones have been widely used for the spectrophotometric determination of metal ions, but heterocyclic thiosemicarbazones are not exploited much. The importance of mercury determination is well known. The analytical monitoring of mercury in environmental, industrial, biological and food samples is extremely important because of high toxicity of this metal both in inorganic and organic compounds. In continuation of our ongoing work on the analytical applications of heterocyclic thiosemicarbazones^{4,5}, we report here the spectrophotometric determination of mercury in different aqueous samples.

This paper describes the non-extractive spectrophotometric determination of mercury(II) as it 3-MTAT complex in aqueous medium. A close literature survey reveals that 3-MTAT are so far not been employed for the spectrophotometric determination of mercury(II).

Results and discussion

The reagent (3-MTAT), are easily obtained just as

any monothiosemicarbazone. The reagent has been characterized using IR, NMR and Mass spectral data. The infrared spectrum of 3-MTAT showed bands (cm^{-1}) 3342(s), 3279(m), 3153(m), 2979(s), 1589(m), 1066(m), are respectively assigned to $\nu(\text{NH})$ asymmetric stretch, $\nu(\text{NH})$ symmetric stretch, $\nu(=\text{C}-\text{H})$ aromatic stretch ($\text{sp}^2 \text{ C}-\text{H}$), $\nu(\text{C}-\text{H})$ aliphatic stretch ($\text{sp}^3 \text{ C}-\text{H}$), $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ Schiff's base and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ vibrations respectively. ^1H NMR spectra ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$) showed signals (δ ppm) at 2.39, 7.64 and 11.65; due to $-\text{CH}_3$ thiophene and $\text{N}=\text{C}-\text{H}$ protons of 3-MTAT respectively. Mass spectra shows molecular ion signal at m/z 199. Based on above spectral data, the structure of the reagent is given in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Structure of heterocyclic thiosemicarbazone (3-MTAT)

Absorption spectra of $2 \times 10^{-5} M$ solution of 3-MTAT at different pH values were recorded and pK_a values were determined spectrophotometrically using Phillips and Merritt method⁶. The bathochromic shift from 280–350 nm indicates that in solution on increasing pH the $>C=S$ group of reagent (3-MTAT) is enolized and dissociated (Scheme 1). The values of deprotonation constants of 3-MTAT are 2.6 (pK_1) and 7.6 (pK_2) respectively. The pK_1 and pK_2 values are presumably due to thioine-thiol tautomerism and deprotonation of thiol (SH) group respectively.

Table 1. Chromogenic characteristics of 3-MTAT

Metal ion	λ_{max} (nm)	pH range	Molar absorptivity ^a	Color of the complex
Co ^{II}	370	5.0–7.0	2.1×10^4	Greenish yellow
Cu ^{II}	380	5.0–7.0	2.3×10^4	Yellow
Hg ^{II}	375	6.0–10.0	1.8×10^4	Pale yellow

^aL mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹.

Scheme 1. A general scheme showing enolization and deprotonation of thiol group.

A 0.01 M solution of reagent stable for 10 h, the color reactions of metal ions with the reagent are summarized in Table 1. In these media the ligand presumably exist in enolic form.

The color reactions of reagent with mercury(II) are instantaneous at room temperature. The order of addition of metal ion, reagent and buffer has no effect on the absorbance of complex. Various physico-chemical and analytical characteristics of the mercury complex are summarized in Table 2. Stoichiometry of the complex (M : L = 1 : 2) was determined by Job's continuous variation method⁷ and molar ratio method. Ammonium chloride (0.2 M)-ammonium solution (0.2 M) buffer (pH 8.0, $\mu = 0.2$ and $T = 300 K$) and equimolar solutions of mercury(II) and reagent were used in these studies. The dissociation constant (α) and concentration (c) of the reagent at intersecting point were used in the calculation of stability constant of the complex (see equation).

Table 2. Physico-chemical and analytical characteristics of Hg^{II} complex with 3-MTAT

Sl. no.	Characteristics	Hg(3-MTAT) ₂
1.	λ_{max} (nm)	375
2.	pH-range (optimum)	6.0–10.0
3.	Mean absorbance	0.362 ± 0.0002
4.	Mole of reagent required per mole of metal ion for full color development	10-Fold
5.	Time stability of the complex (h)	4
6.	Beer's law validity range ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	0.8–8.02
7.	Molar absorptivity (L mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	1.8×10^4
8.	Specific absorptivity ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-1}$)	0.093
9.	Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g/cm}^2$)	0.0107
10.	Composition of complex as obtained from Job's and molar ratio methods (M : L)	1 : 2
11.	Stability constant of the complex	2.97×10^{11}
12.	Standard deviation in the determination of 4 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of Hg ^{II}	0.0042
13.	Relative standard deviation (RSD%)	1.17
14.	Y-intercept	-0.00066
15.	Angular coefficient (m)	0.091
16.	Correlation coefficient (v)	0.9999
17.	Detection limit ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) ^a	0.035
18.	Determination limit ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) ^b	0.105

$$\text{a}^{\text{Detection limit}} = \frac{\text{Standard deviation} \times 3}{\text{Mean}} (\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}).$$

$$\text{b}^{\text{Determination limit}} S/N = 10.$$

Stability constant of 1 : 2 (M : L) complex is given by $(1 - \alpha)/4\alpha^3 C^2$.

Tolerance limits of foreign ions : The effect of foreign ions which often accompany mercury has been studied by adding different amounts of foreign ions to fixed amount of mercury(II) in solution. The color reaction was studied as described in the standard procedure. An error of 2% in the absorbance of the reaction mixture was considered tolerable. The results are given in Table 3. Larger amounts of Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Cu^{II} do not interfere in the presence of masking agents. Interference of zinc(II) is masked with thiocyanate and copper(II) masked with citrate.

Applications : The present method was successfully applied for the determination of mercury when present alone. The devolved method was also applied to the determination mercury(II) in water samples, biological samples and soil samples (Table 4). The results obtained

Table 3. Tolerance limit ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) of foreign ions in the determination of 4.0 ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) of mercury

Ion added	Tolerance limit 3-MTAT	Ion added	Tolerance limit 3-MTAT
Citrate	400	W^{V}	325
Tartarate	305	$\text{Cd}^{\text{II } a}$	23
Urea	280	$\text{Zn}^{\text{II } a}$	13
Iodide	254	Cr^{VI}	15
Bicarbonate	245	Pb^{II}	8
Thiocyanate	230	Tl^{II}	5.4
Sulphate	190	Pt^{IV}	4
Oxalate	176	Au^{III}	4.8
Thiourea	152	Co^{II}	12
Nitrate	124	Fe^{II}	4.5
Acetate	118	Pd^{II}	8
Phosphate	21	V^{V}	1
Bromide	16	$\text{Cu}^{\text{II } b}$	2.5
Chloride	7		
Fluoride	4.0		

^aIn the presence of 200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of thiocyanate. ^bIn the presence of 300 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of citrate.

Table 4. Determination of mercury in soil, water and biological samples

Name of the sample	Amount of mercury ^a found ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)		
	3-MTAT method	Dithizone method	T-test
Road side soil	1.593	1.553	1.64
Agriculture soil	0.895	0.894	0.41
Urban soil	0.885	0.986	4.18
Drain water ^b	3.344	3.228	1.07
Lab water ^c	1.677	1.683	0.31
Sea water ^d	1.105	1.002	0.57
Tap water ^e	1.091	1.040	0.27
River water ^f	0.897	0.919	1.16
Brain damage patient	1.325	1.296	1.07
Kidney damage patient	1.347	1.314	1.33
Paralysis patient	2.227	2.209	0.72
Sheep liver	1.397	1.374	0.93
Fish liver	1.389	1.338	2.06

^aAverage of five determinations. ^bAnantapur Drain water. ^cLaboratory water (Department of Chemistry, S. K. University, Anantapur). ^dBay of Bengal (Nellore). ^eAnantapur municipal storage tank water. ^fTungabhadra river water (Kurnool).

in the analysis of different samples are comparable to the data obtained using dithizone method⁸. The present method

is simple, rapid and sensitive for non-extractive spectrophotometric determination of mercury(II) in aqueous medium.

Experimental

Preparation of 3-MTAT : The reaction mixture containing 3-methylthiophene-2-carboxaldehyde (3 ml, 0.0030 mol) in 5 ml of methanol, thiosemicarbazide (0.284 g, 0.0030 mol), dissolved in 10 ml of hot water were taken in 250-ml round bottom flask. Suitable quantity (~ 2 ml) of glacial acetic acid was added to the reaction mixture and refluxed with stirring for 3 h. Light brown colored product was separated out on cooling the reaction mixture. It was collected by filtration and washed several times with hot water and 50 percent cold methanol. This compound was recrystallised from methanol and dried *in vacuum*. Percentage of yield is 93; m.p. 188–190 °C.

The reagent solution (0.01 M) was prepared by dissolving 50 mg of the compound in dimethylformamide (DMF) in 25 ml volumetric flasks. The reagent solution was stable for at least 10 h.

Hydrochloric acid (1 M)-sodium acetate (1 M) (pH 0.5–3.5); 0.2 M sodium acetate-0.2 M acetic acid (pH 4.0–6.5) and 0.2 M ammonium chloride-0.2 M ammonium solutions (pH 7.5–10.5) were used in the present study.

A 1×10^{-2} M stock solution of divalent mercury was prepared by dissolving 0.272 g of mercuric chloride (Merck, Darmstadt) in deionized water containing few drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid and made up to the mark in a 100-ml volumetric flask. Aliquots of this solution were standardized⁹ with EDTA using xylenol orange as an indicator. Dilute solutions were prepared from this stock solution. Solutions of large numbers of inorganic ions complexing agents were prepared from their AnalaR grade or equivalent grade water soluble salts.

Recommended procedure : An aliquot of the solution containing mercury in optimum concentration range (Table 2), 10 ml of buffer solution (pH 8.0) and 1 ml 0.01 M reagent solution were combined in 25-ml volumetric standard flasks and resulting solution was diluted to the mark with distilled water. The absorbance of the solution was measured at 375 nm against reagent (3-MTAT) blank. The measured absorbance was used compute the amount of mercury from predetermined calibration plot.

Instrumentation : Perkin-Elmer (Lambda 25) UV-Visible spectrophotometer equipped with 1.0 cm (path length) quartz cell and Elico model Li-610 pH meter were used in the present study.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank UGC and DST, New Delhi for financial support. The authors also thank S. Siva Sankar Reddy of IICT, Hyderabad for his help in recording IR and NMR spectra of reagent samples.

References

1. R. B. Singh, B. S. Garg and R. P. Singh, *Talanta*, 1978, **23**, 619.
2. K. Hussain Reddy and D. Venkata Reddy, *Q. Chem. Rev.*, 1985, **1**, 47.
3. B. S. Garg and V. K. Jain, *Mikrochem. J.*, 1988, **38**, 114.
4. N. B. L. Prasad, K. Hussain Reddy and T. S. Reddy, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2003, **42**, 112.
5. K. Hussain Reddy, N. B. L. Prasad, T. S. Reddy and M. Syaji Rao, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **83**, 980.
6. J. P. Phillips and L. L. Merritt, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 410.
7. P. Job, *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, **9**, 113.
8. Z. Marczenko, "Spectrophotometric Determination of Elements", Wiley Interscience, New York, 1976.
9. A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd ed., ELBS, Longman, 1975.